

**THE THERAPEUTIC ROLE OF CHANTING AND LISTENING
VISHNU SAHASTRANAMA MANTRA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF
JWARA: A LITERATURE REVIEW STUDY**

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is a traditional Indian medical science based on systematic principles of physiology, pathology, and therapeutics aimed to maintain overall health by balancing *doshas* and to maintain healthy condition.

Jwara (fever) as the king of all diseases.^[1] *Jwara* is marked by irregular fever patterns due to disturbed *doshas*, mainly *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*.^[2] Modern lifestyle, stress, and low immunity often aggravate such conditions. Alongside herbal and dietary treatment, mental health wellbeing and *Mantra Chikitsa* play an important role.

Daivavyapashraya Chikitsa is one of the treatment approaches concerned with Spiritual way of treatment. *Mantra Chikitsa* is one of the *Chikitsa*, belongs to *Daivavyapashraya Chikitsa*. *Vishnu Sahastranama*, a powerful Vedic hymn consisting of 1000 names of *Lord Vishnu*, is said to harmonize body, mind,

and soul through sound vibrations. Chanting of *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* is believed to calm the mind, balancing *doshas*, improving immunity, and supporting faster recovery.^[3]

Modern studies have shown *Mantras* can influence the autonomic nervous system, reduce cortisol, and promote immune resilience.^[4] *Acharya Charak* stated in *chikitsa sthana* in *Jwara Chikitsa Adhaya*, about the effects of *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* on the management of *Jwara*.^[5]

...विष्णु सहस्रमूर्धानं चराचरपतिं विभुम् ॥

स्तुवन्नामसहस्रेण ज्वरान् सर्वानपोहति ।... (Cha. Chi. 3/311)

The *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra*, scientifically referenced, originates from the *Anushasana Parva* of *Mahabharat* and was first composed and presented by *Acharya Vyasa*.^[6]

...ॐ शान्ताकारं भुजगशयनं पद्मनाभं सुरेशं, विश्वाधारं गगनसदृशं मेघवर्णं शुभाङ्गम् ।

लक्ष्मीकान्तं कमलनयनं योगिभिर्ध्यानगम्यं, वन्दे विष्णुं भवभयहरं सर्वलोकैकनाथम् ॥^[7]...

From previous studies it is already proven that *Mantra Chikitsa* through recitation has demonstrated reduced stress and improved cardiovascular and cognitive parameters. The *Vishnu Sahastranama*, in particular, has been associated with enhanced calmness, homeostasis, and recovery from.^[8]

This research seeks to examine whether integrating *Mantra Chikitsa*, particularly the chanting of the *Vishnu Sahasranama Mantra*, can enhance the management of *Jwara*.

Need of Study

In Modern medical practices, as well as in some cases of Ayurvedic management, it has been seen that, *Jwara* is not completely cured in all patients. Despite following conventional methods, some cases remain resistant and recurrent. *Acharya Charak* has mentioned that, chanting *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* as a part of *Devavyapashraya Chikitsa* for *Jwara* management in *Charak Chikitsa Sthana*. Hence, this study is needed to observe and study the effects of *Vishnu Sahastranam Mantra* as a supportive therapy in *Jwara*, for complete recovery and well-being.

AIM OF STUDY

To observe the effects of the *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* in the management of *Jwara*.

OBJECTIVES

1. To observe the effects of *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* chanting the patients suffering from *Jwara*.
2. To assess the physiological effects of *Vishnu Sahastranamam* on patients.

Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H_0): Chanting of *Vishnu Sahastranamam Mantra* has no significant effect on *Jwara* treatment.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): Chanting of *Vishnu Sahastranamam Mantra* has significant effect on *Jwara* treatment.

Type of Study

Literary and Observational Study.

METHODOLOGY

A. Literature Review

The references will be collected and discussed from Ayurveda classics, commentaries, modern literature, PubMed, Google Scholar, Ayush research portal, and Internet gateways. These will be analysed and compiled to explain the role of *Mantra Chikitsa* and *Jwara*.

B. Observational Study

I. Study type: Observational study

II. Sample Size: 50 participants.

III. Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with *Jwara*.
2. Age group: 18 to 30 years.
3. Both male and female participants.
4. Patients willing to participate voluntarily and gives consent.
5. Patients with mild fever ($98-99^{\circ}\text{F}$)⁹ who are stable and able to sit or listen to the chanting session.
6. Patients receiving standard Ayurvedic or modern treatment, along with the addition of *Vishnu Sahastranama* chanting as a supportive therapy.

IV. Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients suffering from severe, chronic, or infectious fevers (e.g., typhoid, malaria, dengue, etc.) requiring intensive medical care.]
2. Individuals with serious systemic illnesses (e.g., cardiac, renal, hepatic, or neurological disorders).
3. Patients with psychiatric disorders or cognitive impairment.
4. Children below 18 years and adult above 30 years.
5. Individuals unwilling or unable to participate or unable to follow the chanting/listening procedure regularly.
6. Patients under strong sedatives or antipyretic dependency affecting observation outcomes.

V. Table No. 1: Study Design.

S. No.	Component	Details
1.	Treatment Given	<i>Vishnu Sahasranama Mantra</i> chanting twice daily
2.	Chant protocol	Twice daily (morning and evening), 30 minutes per session, seated, aided by chanting/listening.
3.	Assessment schedule	Morning: demographics, temperature. Evening: repeat measures + patient feedback. Follow-up: Regular Monitoring.
4.	Data collection methods	Daily temperature log of patient, symptom diary, standardized questionnaires (Likert scale), session chanting/listening, attendance logs.
5.	Adherence monitoring	Daily chanting diary, attendance sheet for supervised sessions.

VI. Duration of the Study: 24 hr, (follow-up for 15 days)

VII. Assessment Parameters

Table No. 2: Assessment Tools.

S.No.	Study Type	Scale Chosen
1	Thermometer based (Mercury) (C ⁰ /F ⁰) ⁹	Thermometer readings
2	Observational (without thermometer) Study- Questionnaire	Fever Assessment Scale- Likert Scale ¹⁰
3	Symptomatic Assessment	FAST Scale ¹¹

VIII. Statistical Analysis

1. Meticulously observation will be diligently recorded throughout the study.
2. Statistical analyses ANOVA (Analysis of variance) test will be utilized.

3. Mean, standard deviation, standard error and p-value will be calculated to analyse intra group association in qualitative variables using appropriate software like PRISMA or Sigma software.
4. The obtained result was interpreted based on the following level of Significance:
 - Non- significant: p-value > 0.05
 - Significant: p-value < 0.05
 - Highly Significant: p-value < 0.01
 - Very Highly Significant: p-value < 0.001

Implications

- Patient will get supportive therapy with *Mantra Chikitsa*
- *Mantra Chikitsa* will resolve not only fever but will also deals will other symptoms.
- *Mantra Chikitsa* shows the superiority of *Daivavyapashrya chikitsa* over all.

Future Scope

- Future research can explore how *Mantra* vibrations influence physiological aspects such as temperature regulation, immune response, and stress hormones.
- Further studies can bring modern science with ancient Vedic healing practices through supportive therapy.
- A Clinical study with more intervention parameters can be taken.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Results will be compared to evaluate the holistic benefits of chanting *Vishnu Sahastranama Mantra* on both mental and psychological aspects of *Jwara*.

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